

Beyond Progress: Unmasking the Myth of Scientific-Economic Advancement

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Abstract: This essay discusses the tension between pure science and applied science in contemporary society, using examples such as the DNA nanomotor and the concept of "Dynamic Genostability". The study proposes a review of the objectives of science, arguing that scientific advancements have been increasingly dictated by economic interests at the expense of the principles of pure science. The concept of 'Dynamic Genostability' is used to challenge this bias, suggesting a view in which life is centered on human bioenergetics and DNA transmission. The essay concludes by arguing for the need for a more integrated and conscious approach in science that emphasizes the importance of human life beyond economic exploitation.

Keywords: Pure Science, Applied Science, Universal Biophysical Potential Energy, DNA Nanomotor, Dynamic Genostability, Well-Being, Economic-Scientific Progress, Science and Economy, Scientific Research, Human Biological Integrity.

Introduction

Science, in its relentless journey of discovery and innovation, has traditionally been divided into two distinct realms: pure science, driven by curiosity and the pursuit of knowledge for its own sake, and applied science, oriented towards practical solutions and technological advancements. This division reflects a fundamental tension in the trajectory of scientific research. The recent groundbreaking study by Li et al. (2023) on an endogenous enzyme-powered DNA nanomotor in living cells for microRNA imaging exemplifies this intersection. The study highlights not only technological advancement but also raises questions about the direction and objectives of modern science.

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Parallel to this, the emerging concept of "Dynamic Genostability," introduced in "The Necessary Existence and Death of Organisms to Sustain the Eternity of DNAs" by Orquiza (2023), offers a revolutionary perspective that redefines life on Earth as the manifestation of DNA's quest for perpetuation. Contrary to the traditional organism-centered view, this approach proposes that organisms are transient vehicles for DNA, seeking to maintain its low-entropy state amidst environmental challenges. This viewpoint not only challenges the anthropocentric bias in biology but also suggests a reevaluation of conservation ethics and provides new insights for astrobiology.

The aim of this essay is to explore how these two lines of thought, represented by the DNA nanomotor study and the Dynamic Genostability hypothesis, converge and diverge in their approach to science. The need for a new perspective in science is imperative, especially in an era where scientific advancements are increasingly intertwined with economic and commercial implications. By reevaluating scientific progress through these lenses, this essay seeks to unmask the myth of scientific-economic advancement and highlight the importance of human biophysical integrity at the heart of scientific research.

Thesis

This essay argues that contemporary science, exemplified by the development of technologies such as the DNA nanomotor, has increasingly been driven by economic interests, distancing itself from the principles of pure science. Utilizing the concept of 'Dynamic Genostability' from the article 'The Necessary Existence and Death of Organisms to Sustain the Eternity of DNAs', it proposes a reevaluation of science centered on human bioenergetics and DNA transmission, challenging the instrumentalization of well-being and the myth of scientific-economic progress. The aim is to highlight the intrinsic importance of human life beyond its economic exploitation and suggest a new perspective on the direction of scientific research.

Definition of Terms:

1. **Pure Science:** Research motivated by the desire to understand natural and fundamental phenomena, without immediate focus on practical applications or economic return.

2. **Applied Science:** The field of science that focuses on using scientific knowledge to develop practical, economic, and commercial solutions. Unlike pure science, which pursues knowledge for its own sake, applied science is directed by practical objectives, aiming to solve specific problems, create products or technologies, and is often motivated by immediate economic or social demands. While playing a vital role in technological advancement and innovation, the increasing integration of applied science with economic and commercial interests can sometimes restrict or eclipse the importance of pure science in the uncompromised pursuit of new knowledge.

3. **Universal Biophysical Potential Energy:** A concept that encompasses potential energy as a fundamental principle of physics manifested critically and universally in biological systems. This term highlights the interdependence between physical and biological processes, where principles of energy and thermodynamics are applicable to all forms of life. This energy, coordinated by DNA, plays a vital role in cellular functions, genetic regulation, and metabolic processes, transcending specific contexts or species to be an omnipresent characteristic in all living beings.

4. **DNA Nanomotor:** A cutting-edge technology that uses DNA sequences to create molecular devices capable of performing mechanical work on a nanometric scale.

5. **Dynamic Genostability:** A concept that redefines life on Earth as the manifestation of DNA's quest for perpetuation, suggesting that organisms are transient vehicles for the maintenance of DNA in a low-entropy state.

6. **Well-Being:** A term frequently used to justify economic and scientific policies and practices, but that can be instrumentalized to mask the economic exploitation of individuals.

7. **Scientific-Economic Progress:** The notion that advancements in science and technology are intrinsically linked to economic growth and social well-being.

Pure Science vs. Applied Science

The trajectory of science throughout history reflects a constant tension between disinterested investigation (pure science) and the search for practical applications (applied science). Pure science, dedicated to increasing knowledge and understanding of natural phenomena, has its roots in early civilizations, where the study of natural phenomena was often intertwined with philosophy and mystical aspects. The clear distinction between pure and applied science, as we know it today, only began to form during the Scientific Revolution in the 16th and 17th centuries, with figures like Galileo and Newton laying the foundations for the scientific method.

This progress in pure science over the centuries has been marked by fundamental advancements in various areas, such as the theory of evolution in biology and thermodynamics in physics. However, in the contemporary scenario, there is an increasing emphasis on applied science. This trend is largely driven by economic interests, where research is seen as a means to develop marketable and profitable technologies.

The research by Li et al. (2023) on the DNA nanomotor is an example of this intersection between science and economy. The innovation represented by the DNA nanomotor highlights how modern scientific discoveries are often conducted with an eye towards their applicability and market potential. Although such advances are valuable, they can obscure the importance of pure science and its essential contribution to the advancement of knowledge.

Parallely, the notion of 'Dynamic Genostability,' as introduced by Orquiza (2023), suggests a fundamental reevaluation of the objectives and methods of science. This concept challenges traditional views, proposing that organisms are mere vehicles for the perpetuation of DNA in a low-entropy state. This perspective underscores the importance of pure science in understanding the fundamental mechanisms of life, an approach that transcends practical applications and economic interests.

The relationship between pure and applied science, therefore, is not just a matter of different methodologies, but reflects what we value and seek in science. While applied science meets the immediate demands of society, pure science continues to be the foundation upon which all scientific knowledge is built. Recognizing and valuing both aspects is essential for a balanced and sustainable scientific progress.

Universal Biophysical Potential Energy and Human Existence

Understanding universal biophysical potential energy and its importance in human existence leads us to a more fundamental level of science, where human bioenergetics, particularly the role of ATP (adenosine triphosphate), stands out. ATP, a crucial molecule in the storage and transfer of energy in cells, is the energetic engine that sustains virtually all cellular processes. Its production and use are perfect examples of the intersection between biochemistry, physics, and biology, illustrating the complexity and elegance of biological systems.

In the context of DNA transmission, universal biophysical potential energy assumes an even more crucial role. DNA, carrying the genetic instructions for the development and functioning of all known organisms, requires energy for its replication and maintenance. This process is not just a matter of heredity, but a continuous manifestation of DNA's quest to sustain its own existence through generations.

The concept of "Dynamic Genostability," as presented by Orquiza (2023), enhances this perspective by suggesting that organisms are transient vehicles for the maintenance of DNA in a low-entropy state. This approach shifts the focus of pure science from the organism itself to the continuity and stability of DNA. It challenges the notion that life is predominantly centered on the individual, proposing instead that the true essence of biological existence is the perpetuation of genetic material.

This focus on universal biophysical potential energy and DNA transmission offers a new lens through which we can understand life. It underscores the importance of pure science in exploring the fundamental principles that govern our existence. While applied science seeks to utilize these principles to develop practical solutions, pure science seeks to understand them in their purest and unadulterated form. This deep understanding is crucial, not only for the advancement of science, but also for the appreciation of life in its most fundamental form.

Human Beings and the Economic System

The interaction between the universal biophysical potential energy of human beings and the economic system unfolds a complex narrative, where biology and economy intertwine deeply and intrinsically. Universal biophysical potential energy, a vital force that sustains all biological functions, including the production and use of ATP, is at the core of all human activities. This energy not only fuels cellular processes but also translates into the capacity for work and productivity, fundamental elements for the economy.

However, this intricate relationship exposes a striking duality: human beings, as generators of energy and work, are essential to the economic dynamic, but simultaneously, they can become vulnerable to a system that often prioritizes economic gains over individual and collective well-being. This tension is evident in how technological advancements, such as DNA nanomotors, are directed and valued within the economic context, reflecting

how the economy can shape the priorities and directions of scientific research.

The theory of "Dynamic Genostability," introduced by Orquiza (2023), brings a valuable perspective to this discussion. By focusing on the continuity of DNA as a primary goal of biological existence, it invites reflection on the true role of human beings within the economic system. This approach proposes a view in which human beings are more than mere participants in the economy; they are essential carriers of genetic information, a responsibility that goes beyond their economic value.

Therefore, understanding the relationship between the universal biophysical potential energy of human beings and the economic system requires a careful consideration of human and biological values, beyond economic metrics. This paves the way for a more balanced and sustainable economic model that respects both the economic contribution and the intrinsic dignity of human life.

Well-Being: An Economic Justification

The concept of well-being, often invoked in discussions on scientific and economic policies and practices, deserves a critical analysis to understand how it is instrumentalized in various contexts. Traditionally, well-being is presented as a desirable and benevolent goal, associated with health, happiness, and prosperity. However, the reality often reveals a more strategic and economic use of this term, especially in spheres where science and economy intersect.

The instrumentalization of well-being as a justification for certain scientific and economic practices can be seen as a way of masking underlying interests, primarily economic. For instance, technological innovations such as DNA nanomotors can be promoted under the banner of "enhancing human well-being" through medical or scientific advancements.

However, such innovations are often also tied to considerable economic interests, whether in the form of research funding, patents, or market potential.

Moreover, the emphasis on well-being can sometimes divert attention from important ethical or ecological issues. While promoting health and happiness is undoubtedly important, the definition and measurement of "well-being" are often shaped by economic and market parameters, rather than being based on a holistic and multidimensional understanding of human life.

This economic approach to well-being is also reflected in how public policies and corporate decisions are shaped. For example, initiatives that claim to promote well-being may, in reality, be more aligned with economic growth or improving productive efficiency, rather than genuinely focusing on improving living conditions or environmental sustainability.

Therefore, it is essential to have awareness and critical reflection on how well-being is used as a justification in scientific and economic contexts. Recognizing and challenging the instrumentalization of this concept is an important step to ensure that scientific and economic practices are truly aligned with the authentic interests and needs of humans, and not just with disguised economic objectives.

Deconstructing the Myth of Scientific-Economic Progress

The concept of progress, both in science and the economy, is often interpreted as a linear and continuous advancement towards a state of greater knowledge, advanced technology, and overall well-being. However, this simplistic view deserves critical examination, as it hides complexities and implications that go beyond the surface of innovations and economic growth. The "myth of scientific-economic progress" refers to the belief that every scientific or technological advancement inevitably results in social and

economic improvements. This optimistic view often overlooks the negative consequences, such as social inequalities, environmental impacts, and the compromise of scientific integrity.

Firstly, it is crucial to recognize that science, while it can be a force for good, does not operate in isolation from social and economic contexts. Scientific research is often influenced by economic interests, where funding and research priorities are shaped by expectations of profitability and practical applicability. This reality can divert science from its fundamental goal of seeking knowledge for knowledge's sake and may limit the exploration of areas that do not promise immediate economic returns.

Additionally, technological progress, while offering innovative solutions to various challenges, can also create new problems, such as technological obsolescence, dependence on non-renewable resources, and ethical issues related to privacy and security. The dissemination of technologies such as DNA nanomotors, for example, opens new frontiers of knowledge and application, but also raises questions about ethical and environmental implications.

In this context, it becomes imperative to reevaluate the objectives of science. Science should aspire to a balance between the disinterested pursuit of knowledge (pure science) and practical applications that benefit society (applied science). A deeper and more reflective dialogue is needed on what constitutes true progress, considering not only technological and economic advances but also human well-being and environmental sustainability.

Deconstructing the myth of scientific-economic progress, therefore, involves critical reflection on how we value and measure advancement, and the pursuit of a more integrated and conscious model of scientific and economic development, which honors both human and environmental aspects.

Discussion

This section of the essay provides a detailed analysis of the implications of the arguments previously presented, offering a profound reflection on the need for a paradigm shift in science.

The discussion begins with the consideration of the dual role of pure and applied science. While pure science seeks an uncompromised understanding of natural phenomena, applied science focuses on practical solutions, often driven by economic interests. This division, functional in many respects, suggests the need for a more integrated approach where the intrinsic value of knowledge is recognized, regardless of its immediate applicability. Science should not be evaluated solely by its ability to generate profit or technological innovations but also by its contribution to a deeper understanding of the world.

The concept of "Universal Biophysical Potential Energy" introduces a perspective that goes beyond anthropocentrism in science. This concept highlights the importance of considering universal principles that govern energy and life in all its forms. By focusing on energy as a fundamental element that interlinks all living beings, we are led to rethink the role of science in understanding and respecting the complexity of life.

The instrumentalization of well-being as a justification for economic and scientific practices is another issue that deserves critical analysis. While well-being is often used as a metric to evaluate the success of policies and innovations, this analysis reveals that it is often shaped by economic parameters, diverting attention from broader ethical, social, and environmental issues.

Finally, deconstructing the myth of scientific-economic progress illuminates the need to reassess what truly constitutes progress. Progress should not be measured only by technological advances or economic growth but also by the impact on quality of life, social equity, and environmental sustainability. This discussion points to the need for a paradigm shift in

science, a paradigm that values knowledge and innovation in a way that is balanced, sustainable, and beneficial for all.

In summary, the discussion in this essay highlights the complexity of the relationships between science, society, and economy. It suggests a paradigm shift in how we understand and practice science, emphasizing the need for more holistic and integrated approaches that recognize the interconnection between all aspects of life and knowledge.

Conclusion

Throughout this essay, we have explored various aspects that challenge the conventional understanding of science and its role in society. The journey began with an analysis of pure versus applied science, highlighting the importance of maintaining a balance between the pursuit of knowledge for its own sake and the practical application of that knowledge. The discussion about universal biophysical potential energy and dynamic genostability revealed the need for a more holistic perspective in science, one that recognizes the universality of biophysical processes and the importance of DNA in coordinating life.

We also examined how well-being has often been instrumentalized in scientific and economic contexts, serving more as a justification for profit-oriented practices than as a true indicator of human progress. Moreover, we deconstructed the myth of scientific-economic progress, highlighting the need to reassess our paradigms of success and advancement.

This essay concludes with a call for a deeper reflection on science and its role in society. Science should not be seen merely as a pathway to technological and economic progress, but as a journey of discovery that respects and values human biophysical autonomy and integrity. True scientific progress should be that which contributes to the holistic well-being of humanity and the planet, considering not only economic benefits but also social and environmental impacts.

Therefore, the challenge that presents itself is to rethink and reshape science in a way that aligns with values of respect, integrity, and sustainability. This involves not only scientists and researchers but the entire society, as science is a collective endeavor that reflects and shapes our beliefs, values, and futures.

Declarations

Conflict of Interest

In this essay, we addressed essential issues about science, its interaction with the economy, and its impact on society. It is important to declare that, during the preparation of this work, no conflicts of interest arose. No external influence, whether commercial, financial, or academic, affected the content, direction, or conclusions presented in this study. The integrity and objectivity of the essay were maintained throughout all stages of its conception and development.

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This essay is a product of the independent effort and research of the author. All work, from initial research to final writing, was carried out exclusively by the author, without external funding or institutional support. This independence ensures that the perspectives and analyses presented are solely the result of the author's interest and academic investigation, free from any external influences or expectations.

Data and Software Repositories

This essay is a theoretical exploration based on concepts, analyses, and reflections derived from research and literature existing in the field of science and the philosophy of science. Due to the conceptual and discursive

nature of this work, no data repositories or software requiring mention or access were used. Therefore, the mention of data and software repositories is not applicable in this context. All information and references used come from publicly available and recognized sources in the academic community. This approach ensures that the essay remains focused on theoretical analysis and interpretation, without the need for empirical data or specific software tools.

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